

Project no. 862820

Project acronym: Build-in-Wood

Project title: Sustainable wood value chains for construction of low-carbon multi-storey buildings from renewable resources

Deliverable D9.3

European Network for Tall Wood Buildings (NTWB) created

Work Package Number and Title:	<i>WP9 Business Development</i>
Lead-beneficiary:	<i>DTI</i>
Contributing Beneficiaries:	<i>NTI, CF Møller, Urbasofia, BMA, WTA, Bimetica, Rothoblaas, rtds, AK, Eggodomus, Habitech, KNAUF, Scandi Byg, hsbcad, EllisDon</i>
Type:	<i>Website</i>
Dissemination Level:	<i>PU</i>
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This deliverable confirms the development, launch and establishment of the Build-in-Wood community with its core purpose to bring the wood construction industry closer together and to make wood a natural choice for all active in this built environment. This purpose is executed through the development of an online global network where members can share knowledge, expand their professional network, and exchange ideas, find project partners as well as to develop their businesses.

The Build-in-Wood community is now open for registration

<https://community.build-in-wood.eu>

Our Vision

Envisioning a world where building with wood is a natural choice, the Build-in-Wood Community is the most valuable global online network to bring people along the whole construction value chain closer together.

Our Mission

Bringing people together to share knowledge and experiences, to inspire, to expand their professional network and exchange ideas, to develop their business as well as to find new project partners.

Please find more information in the attached folder!

For more information please contact:

Build-in-wood-community@dti.dk

Let's build the future

A new way of networking, knowledge sharing and exchanging experiences for everyone working with wood in the construction industry.

community.build-in-wood.eu

Join us now
and be part of
the Community!

WHY ARE WE HERE?

We want to strengthen the community of people working with wood in construction. We do that:

- * Through easy and free access to the community
- * By giving members a way to connect
- * By giving members a place to share and get knowledge
- * By being transparent
- * By facilitating inspiration and knowledge sharing
- * By being independent and noncompetitive

WHAT IS IT ABOUT?

We want to give everyone working in the wood construction industry easy access to international knowledge and network. In the Build-in-Wood Community all members can:

- * Search for wood professionals and enthusiasts around the world
- * Browse people nearby
- * Learn from others
- * Exchange thoughts on common challenges and opportunities
- * Connect with other stakeholders
- * Search by skills and interests
- * Find project partners
- * Join relevant groups
- * Participate in forum discussions
- * Browse organisations
- * Look for or share projects
- * Post jobs, internships, etc.
- * Find and attend events - both events arranged by others and by the Community itself

WHAT'S IN IT FOR ME?

Being part of the Build-in-Wood Community allows you to:

- * Get easy access to knowledge institutions and experts in wood construction - finding the right knowledge is key in developing your business
- * Create your own open or closed networks within the community
- * Get easy access to finding project partners, business partners etc.
- * Get inspiration for your new projects and establish your own wood construction network using the Best Wood Buddies function
- * Be part of a strong international network that gives you access to knowledge sharing in private groups and open forums
- * Organise and announce your own events, find events arranged by others and get newest knowledge for free through the Wood Academy Talks arranged directly in the Community

WHY YOU SHOULD JOIN THE COMMUNITY AND WHAT WE APPEAL TO

THE HEART

THE MIND

THE BUSINESS

Contact:

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**DANISH
TECHNOLOGICAL
INSTITUTE**

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